

An Overview of Leadership Theories and Styles: Proposing Research Agenda through Review of Existing Literature

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Abstract

In this turbulent ever changing business scenario the concept of leadership has gained its significance. It has been debated since ages which leadership style is said to be effective. Many research studies were investigated to know the best style of leadership but the studies proved that there is no universal leadership style acceptable under all situations. Leadership style is considered as one of the crucial factors for engaging the employees. In this article the authors attempted to throw some light on the various leadership styles and theories to give a basic understanding on the evolution and development of leadership over a period of time. The entire study is purely secondary in nature which is collected from past publications, articles over a period of time.

Keywords: Leadership, Leadership Styles and Leadership theories.

Introduction

The concept of leadership is as old as the history of human civilization. Many research studies proved that there is no single style universally acceptable and it all depends upon the situation. The word leadership is originated from the Old English word “**laedere**” which means the one who leads. The big argument in the field of leadership is “**Leaders are born or made**”. According to **W.C.H. Prentice (2004)**, effective leaders always take personal interest in the long-term development of their employees. The past research studies conducted on leadership have given rise to various leadership theories under different time lines (**Muhammad Asrar-ul-Haq & Sadia Anwar, 2018**). However, a lot of research studies are going on to understand what leadership is and still there is a need to understand the existing theories and develop new theories over a period of time. The study starts with the definitions of leadership, various leadership styles and models and its relationship with different outcomes.

Section 1. Definitions and models of leadership

Leadership is the ability to communicate and translate the vision into reality. In an organization leaders must know what is actually happening inside and outside the business. Many senior level leaders are fascinated to hold **capital “L”** leadership roles and this type of leaders do not have any contact with their team or other employees in their organizations (**Michael Boyles, 2023**). **Nash (1929)** Leadership is all about bringing a change in the conduct of people. **Davis (1962)** Leadership is all about binding the team together and motivating to achieve the goals. According to **Fred. E. Fiedler (1964)**, Leader is the person one who “directs and coordinates task-relevant group activities”. **George R. Terry (1972)** defined leadership as a relationship in which one person influences another to attain what the leader desires. **Charles Handy (1992)** A leader always shapes and shares and translates the vision into reality. **Northouse (2010)** defined leadership as “a process where an individual influences a group to achieve a common

goal". **Kathy Mazzarelli (2020)** Leadership is all about helping others to realize their potential and inspiring them to work together for achieving the vision. The early contributions to the leadership studies all started with the development trait theory, behavioural, situational, and new leadership theories. The evolution of the main leadership theories is shown below in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 Source: Evolution of Leadership theory, Albert S. King, Vol.15, No.2, April-June 1990, Indian council of social science research publications.

1. Personality Era: Great man Theory:

The core belief of this theory is that leaders are born, but not made or trained. To be precise this Great man theory states that a few leaders are gifted with unique characteristics to be effective as a leader. Examples were often drawn from popular historical figures such as Julius Caesar, Mahatma Gandhi, Abraham Lincoln and Napoleon Bonaparte. This theory strongly believed that great leaders were natural born leaders with exceptional characteristics of leadership, which enabled them to lead individuals while they shape and written as great leaders in the pages of history. (S. Benmira & M. Agboola, 2021)

Later over a period of time this Great man theory evolved into trait theories. Trait theories argues that leaders can be born as well as made. In other words, this theory states that traits possessed by effective leaders can be inherited or learned through training and practice over a period of time. However, until the year 1950s a consistent set of traits has not been produced. (S. Benmira & M. Agboola, 2021)

The true merits of Great man theory do not rely upon hero worship or nor do they give false arguments on this theory. Forget about the merits but this theory real strength lies in the ability in identifying a core set of leadership traits. From historical point of view this theory is the starting point for discussing about the leadership in many ways and led to the development of other leadership theories over a period of time. (Corey S. Halaychik, 2016)

Trait Period: Trait Theory

The trait theory of leadership, also known as “Great man theory” one of the early contributions by Thomas Carlyle in the 19th century (Northouse 2004, 2007). If we travel to the history how this theory was developed it is in the year 1840, Carlyle delivered six public lectures on the roles played by heroes in shaping of the history. The, following year also those lectures were made together into a single volume entitled on Heroes, Heroes worship, and the Heroic in history, this is how the Great man theory was born. (Carlyle, Thomas 1841). This theory is not scientifically proven because this theory stands on a repeated mantra that leaders are born and not made. To some extent this theory holds true that some individuals are gifted with some qualities that can allow them to see as “natural or gifted” leaders. (Corey S. Halaychik, 2016). Carlyle pointed out that no great man lives in vain. The History of the world is nothing but the Biography of great men. Researchers examined that great leaders like Alexander, Napoleon, Genghis khan and others are natural leaders born with gifted traits. (Thaddeus Hunt, JD & LaVonne C. Fedynich, Ed. D, 2018).

2. Influence Era: This era has been an improvement over the Personality era by recognizing that leadership is a relationship between individuals but not a characteristic of Solitary leader. (Leaders using power as a single point of authority to control). This era divided into two periods: a. Power relations period and b. Persuasion period.

a. Power relations period

During this period attempts were made in understanding and explaining the leader effectiveness in the terms of source and the amount of power exercised. Now a day most of the leaders are using their power to control, but now power is no way regarded as the force to bring change among the followers. (Albert S. King, 1990) Perhaps the best known of the theories is: French and Raven’s five forms of power. This model identified three types of positional power – legitimate, reward, and coercive – and two sources of personal power – expert and referent (your personal appeal and charm). The model also suggested that using personal power is the better alternative, and that you should work on building expert power (the power that comes

with being a real expert in the job) because this is the most legitimate source of personal power. (Mind tools Content Team)

b. Persuasion period

In this period coercion was completely removed but still the leader was considered as a dominant factor in the leader-member dyad. (Albert S. King, 1990) In general persuasion refers in the ability to convince others to support a particular view point. This approach now widely used in many contemporary organisations because majority of the effective leaders applies different styles, and selecting the right style that one that meet the needs of the moment. (Allred 10.com)

3. Behaviour Era: Behavioural theory which is evolved from trait theories asserts that leaders can be made, rather than born and certain particular behaviours can be learnt over a period of time. This theory mainly focuses on the actual behaviour exhibited rather than the traits, and it completely ignores the situation and environment of the leader. (Sihame Benmira, Moyosolu Agboola, 2021) Various research studies was conducted in this era which has shown different patterns of leadership behaviour labelled as styles. This theory became a widespread accepted approach in the field of management training. The best known is being Blake and Mouton's Managerial Grid. (Sihame Benmira, Moyosolu Agboola, 2021) this Behaviour Era is further divided into 3 periods: A. Early behaviour period, 2. Late Behaviour period and 3. Operant period.

1. Early Behaviour Period: In this early period, we will take a look at the emergence of few theories such as: Ohio State Studies (Fleishman, Harris and Burt, 1955) and Michigan State Studies (Likert, 1961) (Albert S. King, 1990) Now we will take deep dig into these theories during the early period.

a. Ohio State Studies: The Ohio state studies is considered as one of the behavioural theories of leadership. This research was conducted by a group of researchers working at Ohio university in studying in depth about leadership behaviour and effectiveness. (Sujan, 2023)

The main purpose of conducting this research study is to spot the independent dimensions of leadership behaviour and to spot out the effect of those dimensions on work-performance and satisfaction. The researchers have identified two sets of behaviours: 1. Initiating structure and 2. Consideration. Initiating structure refers to the extent which the leader clearly defines the goals to be achieved. Leaders who are scoring high in this dimension could achieve higher performance and productivity. (Sujan, 2023) On the other Consideration refers to the extent in which how a leader supports their team, creating supportive relationship and mutual trust and respect among their team members. (Sujan, 2023)

These two leadership dimensions also can be represented within the following Figure 2:

Figure 2: Source: What is Ohio State Studies on Leadership Behaviour, Sujan, July, 6th, 2023, tyonote.com.

Describing the above diagram:

- 1 – Leaders retreats to a generally passive role of allowing the situation to take care of itself.
- 2 – The leader strives to promote group harmony and social needs satisfaction.
- 3 – The leader strives to achieve a productive balance between getting the job done and maintaining a cohesive friendly workgroup.

4 – The leader devotes primary attention to getting the job done. And, personal concerns are strictly secondary.

b. Michigan model of Leadership: Michigan leadership studies is one of the early approaches in Behavioural leadership which was developed by Rensis Likert around 1940s. (Sujan, 2023) This model clearly explains how a leader brings a positive change in the lives of teams, organisation and society. No leader is perfect, all leaders have some weakness, but an effective leader always understands how to complement their weakness and improve day by day and gains trust and support from their team. (D. Scott DeRue, Gretchen Spreitzer, Brian Flanagan, & Benjamin Allen, 2013)

After doing extensive research by studying number of supervisors in several factories, the Michigan group came up with two dimensions of leadership behaviour: 1. Employee-centred and 2. People centred. (Sujan, 2023)

Managers using employee-centred leadership behaviour used to provide sufficient freedom to their team and provided necessary assistance to subordinates. Leaders strongly believed that employee's welfare is more important than forcing them to do the job. On the contrary, production-centred leadership behaviour focused more attention to subordinate's work, explaining work procedures, and regarding team members as a focus. it's also called the job-centred leadership style. (Sujan, 2023)

2.Late Behaviour Period: The Late Behaviour Period advanced the early behaviour period theories by adapting them for managerial application which aid in decision making. In this late behaviour period four models are developed: 1. Managerial Grid, 2. Four-Factor theory, 3. Action theory of leadership and 4. Theory X and Theory Y.

a. Managerial Grid: This Grid model which was developed by Blake and Mouton (1964) was one of the model used to determine the leadership effectiveness. This model is widely used by most of the organisations across the globe to improve interpersonal relations and leadership skills. This grid model is based upon two assumptions: 1. Concern for people and 2. Concern for Production (H. John Bernardin and Kenneth M. Alvares, 1976) The two factors identified by Blake and Mouton are not new because the earlier studies on leadership like Ohio studies identified two leadership dimensions called as Consideration and Initiating structure which has a very close resemblance to the dimensions developed under this Grid model. But this model contribution is that it identified 5 leadership styles based on the two factors. (H. John Bernardin and Kenneth M. Alvares, 1976) Each style is identified by its position on a scale of 1-9 for concern for people and concern for production. To understand better about this Grid model it is depicted below through this Figure 3.

Figure 3: Source: The Managerial Grid Model, Mark Bridges, March 16, 2021, Flevyblog online business magazine.

Describing the above diagram:

(1,1): Impoverished management: Managers that score low on concern for production and low on concern for people.

(1,9): Country Club Management: Managers that score low on concern for production and high on concern for people.

(9,1): Produce or Dictatorial style: Managers scoring high on concern for production and low on concern for people.

(5,5): Middle of the Road: Managers scoring medium on concern for production and medium on concern for people.

(9,9): Team Management: Managers score high on concern for production and high on concern for people (**Lars de Bruin, 2020**)

b. Four-factor theory: This theory of leadership was developed by Bowers and Seashore in the year 1966 by studying various individuals in leadership roles at 40 life insurance offices. The four factors identified are: 1. Support 2. Interaction Facilitation 3. Goal emphasis and 4. Work facilitation. (**Nacie Carson, 2021**) The final results of this theory suggests that the four factors originally proved the fact is these four factors exist as a separate measurable entity with slight exceptions. (**James C. Taylor, 1971**)

c. Action theory of Leadership: This leadership model was propounded by John Adair. This model is largely based on three overlapping circles: 1. Achieve the task, 2. Build and maintain the team and 3. Develop the individual. (**Sean McPheat, 2020**) Unlike other leadership theories, this model is based on the belief that effective leadership was not simply a trait one was born with but certain leadership qualities can be learnt by anyone through actionable steps and best practices.

d. Theory X and Theory Y: In the year 1960, Douglas McGregor, an American social psychologist, has published a book titled “Human side of Enterprise”. In this book he developed two major theories named as X and Y theory which showed us a new style of management and human motivation. (**Jacques Touma, 2021**)

Theory X is completely viewed as an autocratic management style where the manager completely holds up the power and takes decision without taking the opinion of colleagues at work. McGregor opined that theory X stresses on the satisfaction of the lower needs where extrinsic rewards are on pay and benefits only. According to this X theory it believes that people by nature dislike and avoid work. In order to make them work they should be forced, monitored, controlled and directed either by punishment or rewards. (**Jacques Touma, 2021**)

On contrary theory Y focuses on the integration of goals, stress on average person’s intrinsic interest on his/her work, his desire to take responsibility and to be creative in solving business problems. (**John J. Morse & Jay W. Lorsch, 1970**) This theory has well suited to small business owners, independent professionals etc. But in understanding and implementing these two theories in workplace is quite challenging. If the manager is older who grew up with X theory, it’s a huge leap of faith to implement theory Y because your employees may not believe you as a manager that you have changed. (**Bill Fotsch and John Case, 2017**) Theory Y is based upon an incomplete theory of human motivation that assumes that all people are creative. But the research study conducted by Michael Kirton found out a different model of creativity that explained the failure of theory Y and justified theory X as an important managerial theory. (**Michael P. Bobic & William Eric Davis, 2003**) In understanding this Y theory by Peter and Minahan in their research study findings proved that most of the theory Y concepts are closely related to appreciative inquiry and social construction. (**Peter F. Sorensen & Matt Minahan, 2011**) To understand better about this theory X and theory Y it is depicted below through this Figure 4.

Figure 4: Source: Theory X and Theory Y, by John Dudovskiy, Business Research Methodology Net.

4. Situation Era: The Situation era always focused on how Great leaders are adopting themselves according to the given situation and performing and staying on top of their top duties. In this era three periods are emerged: 1. The environment period, 2. The social status period and 3. Non-technical Period. (Academic Library)

- The environment period indicates that always a great leader will be at the right place at the right time. It agrees that no specific individual is vested with leadership, but rather other individuals can rise to the occasion and lead.
- The second period was the social status period and focused on the social aspects of a situation. It suggested that the social status of individuals influenced their leadership style and made them effective or otherwise.
- The third period was the nontechnical period. This period combined the environmental and social status, drawing on its strength and weakness in describing an effective leader.

5. Contingency Era: This model of leadership, was developed by numerous scholars around 1960s, is rooted on the belief that rather than adapting their style to the organization, leaders should fill the roles based on how well they match the situation. According to this theory, a leader can be effective in one situation may be ineffective in another situation. This theory also states that there is no one best style of leadership that transcends across all situations. Due to this reason it is the leaders to choose their leadership style based on the group, situation and objectives to be accomplished. (Gelmar Vidal & Martinez Vivar, 2017) Some of the notable contributions under this Era are: 1. Fred Fiedler's Theory, 2. Hersey – Blanchard Situational model, and 3. Vroom-Yetton-Jago-Decision model.

• **Fred Fiedler's Contingency Theory:**

One of the notable contribution in this contingency era is done by Fred Fiedler's theory. This theory says that a leader's preference plays a significant role to be successful under different situations. To be specific this theory states that leaders who favour a human orientation (High LPC) will do best in the situations which are favourable while task orientation leaders (Low LPC) will be most effective in the unfavourable situations. This theory main idea is to make a balance between individual's preference and situational factors. (Corey S. Halaychik, 2016) The following Figure 5 provides clarity on this theory developed by Fred Fiedler.

Figure 7 : Source: Leadership Theories, Corey S. Halaychik, in Lessons in Library Leadership, 2016, Science Direct.

6. Transactional era: Also called as the New leadership era which talks about transactional, transformational and other theories. For the first time it is believed that focusing on one dimension of leadership cannot address the problems in an organisation. As the world has turned to be more complex and dynamic, a need for emerged leadership theories has gained its importance. This led to the new leadership era, moving away from the old school leadership theories to developing new emerging leadership theories in facing the real challenges of today's ever-changing organisations. (Sihame Benmira & Moyosolu Agboola,2020) Some of the theories developed are: 1. Transactional and, 2. Transformational.

Transactional theory: Downton (1973) is believed to be the first person to coin the terms transactional and transformational leadership. Burns (1978) has distinguished the leadership style's based on the follower's motivation as either transactional or transformational. (Muhammad Asrar-ul-Haq, Sadia Anwar, 2018)

According to Kuhnert and Lewis (1987) opined that transactional leadership style is the substitution of one goal with another to increase both the leadership performance and employee performances in organisations. Another meaning of this theory is to identify the employee's needs and reward them at regular intervals for satisfying those needs so that they perform to the best.(Nguyen Hai Thanh & Nguyen Van Quang , 2022) This theory is also best called as Carrot and Stick method for employees to complete their tasks. Sometimes the leaders may punish those who failed to complete the tasks that's why this theory is based on reward-punishment aspects, one being positive the other being negative. (Nguyen Hai Thanh & Nguyen Van Quang , 2022)

7. Other theories: Leadership theory is dynamic in nature and it cannot be fixed or static as these theories changes over the period of time. Originally leadership theories in early stages are only confined to Great man and Trait theories, specify that leaders are always born and they possess with special characteristics to lead. Later Behavioural theory has emerged leadership is largely measured on the basis of his/her actions as a leader but not only on certain traits. Now there are lot of new leadership theories have emerged like servant, spiritual leadership and inclusive leadership. Servant leadership became very popular because it always gives importance to its followers only. This leadership always focuses on giving continuous support to their team and main mantra comes first is serving. More recently inclusive leadership has gained its importance because it focuses more on people-centric approach. This theory is based

on the principle that focusing more on encouraging the followers to become leaders. (Sihame Benmira & Moyosolu Agboola, Benmira S, Agboola, 2021)

8. Conclusion

Leadership theories are not static new theories takes their birth over a period of time. If we observe the origins of leadership theories it all has begun with Great man theory, Trait and followed by behavioural and contingent theories. At present in modern era several new leadership theories has emerged like servant, spiritual and inclusive leadership. These modern leadership theories focus mainly on continuous interactions and interrelationships among the leaders and their followers based on the situation.

References:

1. Understanding leadership by W.C.H. Prentice, 2004, Harvard Business Review.
2. The many faces of leadership: Proposing research agenda through a review of literature, Muhammad Asrar-ul-Haq & Sadia Anwar, Volume 4, Issue 2, December 2018, Pages 179-188, Future Business Journal, Elsevier.
3. Organizational leadership: what it is & why it's important, Michael Boyles, Leadership, Management, Organizational leadership, Harvard Business School Online, 2023.
4. A Contingency Model of Leadership Effectiveness, Fred.E. Fiedler, Advances in experimental social psychology, Volume 1, 1964, Pages 149-190, Elsevier publications.
5. Leadership: What is it? John. P. Kotter, Professor of leadership at Harvard Business School, Chapter 1, Sage Publications.
6. The Effect of Strategic Leadership On Employees Creativity by The Mediation of Voice Behaviour, Riska Syafitri, Ayi Ahadiat, Keumala Hayati, SSRG International Journal of Economics and Management Studies, Volume 8 Issue 1, 91-97, January, 2021.
7. Definitions of leadership by different authors, <https://expertpreviews.com/definitions-of-leadership-by-different-authors-17-definitions-of-leadership>, 4-March-2022.
8. 14 Top CEOs Share Their Definition of "Leadership," What's Your Jacob Morgan, Published in Jacob Morgan, Aug 14, 2020.
9. Leadership, the concept, its origin and evolution, Subha Minz, February 6, 2020, linked in.
10. Evolution of leadership theory, Sihame Benmira & Moyosolu Agboola, Benmira S, Agboola M. BMJ Leader 2021, The Learning Zone.
11. S. Benmira & M. Agboola (2021): The Learning Zone, Evolution of leadership theory, Publication history: Received May 26, 2020, Revised December 5, 2020, Accepted December 12, 2020, First published January 8, 2021. Online issue publication, March 29, 2021, Volume 05, Issue 01, BMJ Journals.
12. Corey S. Halaychik (2016): Leadership Theories, Lessons in Library Leadership, A Primer for Library Managers and Unit Leaders, 2016, Pages 1-56, Science Direct.
13. Northouse, P. G. (2004). Leadership: Theory and Practice. Thousand Oaks, Calif: Sage.
14. Northouse, P. G. (2007). Leadership: Theory and Practice. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications.
15. Carlyle, Thomas (1841): On Heroes, Hero-Worship, & the Heroic in History, Art and Popular culture online database.
16. Corey S. Halaychik (2016): Great man theory: An overview, Lessons in library leadership, A Primer for Library Managers and Unit Leaders, 2016, Pages 1-56, Available online 25 March 2016, Version of Record 25 March 2016, Science Direct.
17. Thaddeus Hunt, JD, LaVonne C. Fedynich, Ed. D (2016): Leadership: Past, Present, and Future: An Evolution of an Idea, Journal of Arts & Humanities Volume 08, Issue 02, 2018: 20-26, ISSN: 2167-9045 (Print), 2167-9053 (Online).
18. Evolution of Leadership theory, Albert S. King, Vol.15, No.2, April-June 1990, Indian council of social science research publications.
19. Albert S. King, (1990): Evolution of leadership theory, Vol.15, No.2, April-June 1990, Sage Journals.
20. Core Leadership Theories, Learning the Foundations of Leadership, By the Mind Tools Content Team.
21. The Persuasive leader: Persuasive leadership for a better life and a better world, <http://allred10.com/>.
22. Sihame Benmira, Moyosolu Agboola (2021): Evolution of leadership theory, received 26 May 2020 Revised 5 December 2020 Accepted 12 December 2020 Published Online First 8 January 2021, BMJ Leader Journals.
23. Sihame Benmira, Moyosolu Agboola (2021): Evolution of leadership theory, received 26 May 2020 Revised 5 December 2020 Accepted 12 December 2020 Published Online First 8 January 2021, BMJ Leader Journals.
24. Albert S King (1990): Evolution of Leadership theory, Vol.15, No.2, April-June 1990, Sage Publications.
25. Sujana (2023): What is Ohio State Studies on Leadership Behaviour, tyonote.com.
26. Developing Adaptive Leaders for Turbulent Times: The Michigan Model of Leadership by D. Scott DeRue, Gretchen Spreitzer, Brian Flanagan, & Benjamin Allen, The European Business Review May - June 2013.

27. H. John Bernardin and Kenneth M. Alvares(1976): The Managerial Grid as a Predictor of Conflict Resolution Method and Managerial Effectiveness, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 21, No. 1 (Mar., 1976), pp. 84-92 (9 pages) ,Published By: Sage Publications, Inc.
28. Mark Bridges (2021): The Managerial Grid Model, March 16, 2021, Flevyblog online business magazine.
29. Lars de Bruin (2020): Blake and Mouton Managerial Grid: A Behavioural Approach towards Management and Leadership, *Business to you. com*.
30. Nacie Carson (2021): Four factors of the Theory of Leadership, Published on 1st January, 2021, Bizfluent.
31. James C. Taylor (1971): An empirical examination of a four-factor theory of leadership using smallest space analysis, *Organization Behaviour and Human Performance*, Volume 6, Issue 3, May 1971, Pages 249-266.
32. Sean McPheat (2020): Adair's Action Centred Leadership Model, MTD Training. Com.
33. Jacques Touma (2021): Theories X and Y in Combination for Effective Change during Economic Crisis, *Journal of Human resource and Sustainability studies*, vol.09, no.01, March 2021.
34. John J. Morse & Jay W. Lorsch (1970): Beyond Theory Y, *Employee Performance Management*, Harvard Business Review Magazine.
35. Bill Fotsch and John Case(2017): The challenge of being a Theory Y Manager, Editor's Pick, Forbes.
36. John Dudovskiy, Theory X and Theory Y, *Business Research Methodology Net*.
37. Michael P. Bobic & William Eric Davis (2003): A Kind word for theory X: Or why so many Newfangled Management Techniques Quickly Fail, *Journal of Public administration and research theory*, Vol. 13, No. 03, PP: 239-264, JSTOR.
38. Peter F. Sorensen & Matt Minahan (2011): McGregor's legacy: the evolution and current application of Theory Y management, *Journal of Management History*, ISSN: 1751-1348, Publisher: Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
39. Academic Library, free online college e- textbooks, e-bray.net.
40. Gelmar Vidal & Martinez Vivar (2017): Contingency theory to study leadership styles of small businesses owner-managers at Santo Domingo, Ecuador, *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, Open access, Research article, First published online December 5, 2017, Sage Journals.
41. Corey S. Halaychik (2016): Leadership Theories, Corey S. Halaychik, in *Lessons in Library Leadership*, 2016, Science Direct.
42. Sihame Benmira & Moyosolu Agboola (2020): Evolution of leadership theory, *The Learning Zone*, Volume 5, Issue 1, 2020, BMJ Journals.
43. Muhammad Asrar-ul-Haq, Sadia Anwar (2018): The many faces of leadership: Proposing research agenda through a review of literature, Volume 4, Issue 2, December 2018, Pages 179-188, *Future Business Journal*, Elsevier.
44. Nguyen Hai Thanh & Nguyen Van Quang (2022): Transformational, Transactional, Laissez-faire Leadership Styles and Employee Engagement: Evidence From Vietnam's Public Sector, Research article, First published online May 27, 2022, Open Access, Sage Journals.